

Innovative Technologies to Improve the Spirituality of the Youth during the Global Changes

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 05 July 2022</p> <p>Corresponding author: Tashmetov Tukhtasin Khudayberganovich</p>	<p>In today's era of global changes, special attention is being paid to the effective use of innovations based on new ideas and best international practices in the system of continuing education in the Republic of Uzbekistan. After all, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev said, "Innovation is the future. If we start building our great future today, we must start it on the basis of innovative ideas, innovative approaches." Indeed, behind the experience of leading foreign countries in ensuring the quality and effectiveness of education, which is effectively applied in the practice of the republican system of continuing education, a special place belongs to modern interactive methods, which are the basis of innovative technologies to increase learning activity.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: : globalization, spirituality, national idea, culture, ideology, mass culture, immunity, education, technology, innovation, information, communication, computer, multimedia, internet, interactive, method, learning process, thinking, activism.</p>	

It should be noted that the changes taking place in the economic, social, political and cultural spheres of our country also depend on the education system, which determines the intellectual potential of our country in the future and is a key condition for its development. After all, the main goal of the radical reforms being carried out in our society is, first of all, to bring up the younger generation as spiritually mature and perfect people. In this regard, the role of the system of continuing education is extremely unique. Therefore, the growth of spiritual and intellectual potential of young people, its development at the qualitative level will not only have an impact on increasing the effectiveness of education, the improvement of the system in this area, but also the growth of all areas of this social system.

Modern demand requires educational institutions to combine theory and practice. Only in this way will we be able to bring up a spiritually mature person, a generation of healthy thinking in the future. One of the priorities of our society is to bring up a harmoniously developed generation. After all, only spiritually mature people can create a great future.

The role and importance of modern teaching methods, ie interactive methods, which are the basis of innovative technologies, in the educational process of educational institutions is incomparable. Knowledge, experience and application of pedagogical technologies and their application

in education ensures that students have knowledgeable and mature skills. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev noted, "Uzbekistan must be globally competitive in the field of science, intellectual potential, modern personnel, high technology" [1].

Innovation means to innovate, to create, to change something [2].

In the system of continuing education, innovation in raising spirituality is aimed at improving the quality of the field. Innovations are relevant, important, and consist of new approaches formed in the system of spirituality. These approaches are born on the basis of initiatives and innovations and serve as a promising basis for the development of the conceptual content of national spirituality.

Any innovation in the promotion of spirituality cannot be an innovation. Therefore, it is necessary to point out the main differences between the concepts of "novation" and "innovation". The clear form, content and scope of reform activities serve as a basis for this. If the activity is short-lived and does not have the character of an integrated system, if it has set itself the task of changing only some elements of a particular system, then we are thinking about novation. The concept of innovation is formed if the activity is carried out on the basis of a certain conceptual approach and its result leads to the development of the system or its printsepial change. The criteria for both concepts are as follows:

innovation is carried out within the existing theory, limited in scope and time, methods are updated, and the result improves the previous system. Innovation, on the other hand, will be systematic, good and sustainable, will design a new system of activities in a particular practice, will completely update the positions of the subjects of practice. At the same time, the directions of activity will be opened, modern technologies will be created, new qualitative results of activity will be achieved, and as a result, the practice itself will be updated.

Innovative changes in the development of spirituality, the introduction of any innovation in the system is carried out directly by updating and modifying the activities of the representative of the industry. Innovative activity is a continuous work on the basis of innovations, which is formed and improved over a long period of time [3]. Innovative activity is aimed at solving a number of problems that have arisen as a result of inconsistency of traditional norms with new social requirements or the conflict of the emerging norm of practice with the emerging norm. Innovations have a great impact on the development of ideological views through the constant introduction of innovations into socio-political life.

Pedagogical innovation is a process of preparing specialists to work in new conditions. It is desirable to create and implement new approaches to creative approaches based on previously acquired knowledge and skills.

The goals of innovative education are:

- ensuring a high level of spiritual, intellectual and personal development of students;
- creation of new technologies, projects on the basis of new modern approaches and creation of new, appropriate types of curricula with their help;
- creating conditions for students to acquire scientific thinking skills;
- teaching the methodology of innovation in the socio-economic and professional spheres;
- linking theory with practice and practice with production;
- strengthening the base of teaching materials;
- strengthening the social and economic foundations of the educational environment [4].

One of the main tasks is to further improve the quality of training of the harmoniously developed generation, which is one of the urgent tasks in educational institutions. Therefore, it is expedient to thoroughly review the system of education in all educational institutions in our country, using world experience, and put into practice the most optimal aspects. These are processes that are inherent in modern

innovative requirements that are taking place in the current era of globalization.

The use of modern educational technologies in the classroom, the achievement of high efficiency in the teaching process, as well as interactive technologies that are the basis of innovative technologies activates the activities of students in the deepening of the national idea, national ideology, encourages them to think independently, activism, solidarity, teamwork, caring for each other and effectively affects the enrichment of knowledge. We have based several methods on the effective use of higher human concepts such as national idea, national ideology, national pride in teaching the teaching process through innovative technologies.

SCORE - 2

Using the interactive method "SCORE-2", the training can be conducted in the following order:

After dividing the students into groups (preferably no more than 4 group members), the teacher distributes written information about this method to each group member and teaches them to study it individually, setting a time. At the end of the allotted time, the group members share their knowledge and information about the SCORE method with each other, think about the essence, content, purpose, methodology of this method (within the allotted time). Once the teacher know that they have a general understanding of this method, they talk about the global problems of the time. Using the Brainstorming method, the teacher works with group members to create a list of global issues: “Popular Culture,” “Drugs,” “AIDS,” “Alcoholism,” “Exporting Democracy,” “Indifference,” “Missionary and Proselytism,” “Iudomania”, “human trafficking” and so on. The teacher asks each group to select one problem from this list of global problems, then gives them pre-prepared handouts to think about the problem they have chosen and express their opinions in writing. The group members write down their ideas about the problems they have chosen together on the given papers, preparing one person from the group for the presentation. Once the groups have completed their work, the presentation will begin. The teacher concludes the lesson topic and group work based on the presentations, giving additional feedback. At the end of the session, a film or photos about the global problems of the time, a music video can be shown.

Note: At the beginning of the session, you can choose a global problem by showing a movie, music video, photo, without collecting global problems using the "Brainstorming" method.

Topic: Manifestations of alien and harmful ideas, the role and importance of the national idea in their prevention

Task:

Problem: _____

Symptoms (S – symptom)– what are the symptoms of this problem?

Causes (C – cause) – what are the causes of this problem?

Outcome (O – outcome) – what are the outcomes of this problem? _____

Resources (R – resources) – What resource can help to prevent this problem? Which resource is effective?

Effect (E – effect) – What effects can be obtained by tackling with this problem?

[5]

Peculiarities of the organization of the educational process

Problem: A few years ago, the alarming phrase “Blue Whale” appeared on social networks of our country. Reports of the Blue Whale have highlighted its actions. However, at present there are no analytical, scientific and methodological recommendations that teach how to deal with this scourge. True, it says, “Beware.” But how can parents protect their children from the Blue Whale? Legitimate questions arise. Today, every parent should have clear answers to these specific questions. In today’s global information world, a game called “Blue Whale” has made everyone think. The first rumors about this problem on the Internet started in 2015. There are various facts and information on the Internet about “death groups” such as “Blue Whale”, “Peace House”, “f58”, “f57”: Getting into the teenager by giving him easy, fun assignments at the beginning. He then draws a picture of a blue whale on his body with a knife, listens to one song for 3 days non-stop, and praises and congratulates the teenagers who completed the assignments. This is called a death game, which finally teaches you to complete the last 50 days (assassination) in 50 days and videotape it.

Symptom (S-symptom) - The main causes of this problem’s symptom are disrupting the spiritual world of the growing generation by affecting its mind, heart and inner world.

Reasons (C-cause) - The “blue whale” is a new spiritual threat that is attacking the minds of teenagers! Because, first of all, this trend-threat has targeted young people under the age of 18. So, the teenagers of Uzbekistan. Second, it focuses on capturing young people’s free time, will, and interests [6]. Third, it wants to enslave young people

ideologically and sacrifice them using his own hands and feet. Fourth, its goals contradict our Action Strategy, youth policy, the goals of Uzbek parents, teachers and our youth.

Outcome (O-outcome) The time itself requires comprehensive ideological armament so that young people are not exposed to such a variety of alien and harmful ideas [7]. Therefore, the works of Al Beruni, Ibn Sino, Imam Bukhari, Imam Termezi, Burhaniddin Marghinani, Abu Mansur Moturudi, Alisher Navoi and other great scholars should remain the main idea of our national education and enjoy the exemplary qualities mentioned in their works.

Resource (R-resources) First of all, we need to warn our youth against such threats and carry out advocacy work to strengthen ideological immunity. Second, in addition to learning foreign languages, sports and other hobbies, young people should pay special attention to the formation of advocacy groups [8]. Only then will teenagers be free from the influence of any external forces. Third, the development of effective methods and techniques for the widespread introduction of modern information and computer technologies that ensure the effectiveness of spiritual and educational competitions, trainings, events and advocacy in the community, in continuing education systems.

Effect (E-effect) - For us, the only ideology is the development of Uzbekistan, the prosperity of Uzbekistan. When does spirituality become an invincible force? Only when the talent and courage of young people, their dreams and goals become an example of courage, creativity and perseverance, we will be able to bring up a spiritually mature person, a healthy generation. Because this is the demand of the time today.

VENN DIAGRAM

**Topic: The role of the national idea in strengthening ideological immunity in youth
Peculiarities of the organization of the educational process**

In conclusion, it should be noted that the development of the spiritual sphere in the system of continuing education through the introduction of new innovative technologies directly ensures the effectiveness of education. It is expedient to further enhance the principles of educating young people in the spirit of national and universal values on the basis of innovative technologies. Because it is the result of a strong need to realize our national identity. Universal values are always nourished by national values, and serve to form and promote national spirituality. This is the demand of the time today.

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